

ACCELERATED FATIGUE TESTING FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Special experimental set up using flexural vibration of rod at resonance frequency is used to characterize damage during fatigue test. Experimental results are presented on advanced composite materials.

I) INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials with carbon or silicon carbide (SiC) as matrix are adopted for their remarkable mechanical properties. Fatigue behaviour of such materials is different from that concerning classical composites or metals. With a maximum stress level up to 80 % of static fracture stress, duration of life in fatigue test often exceeds ten million of cycles. In this condition, classical fatigue tests, with working frequency not exceeding 10 Hertz, takes too much time. If we try to increase the frequency to 100 Hertz (or higher), then the test duration will be reduced from 10 days to one day approximately. Successively the principle of experimental set-up, dynamic damage indications and some experimental results are presented.

II) FLEXURAL TEST USING CANTILEVER ROD

Figure (1) represents schematic diagram of the experimental set-up. Sample is a clamped-free rod with additional mass at the free end. The boundary conditions suggested constitutes a compromise between high resonance frequency and high (extensional) stress level at clamped end due to the presence of additional mass. Classical Bernoulli-Euler equation of motion is used. (If necessary, for higher vibration mode and shorter specimens, Timoshenko equation is preferred).

$$E^* I \frac{\partial^4 w^*}{\partial x^4} + \rho S \frac{\partial^2 w^*}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

E^* complex Young modulus, I inertia area moment, ρ density, S cross section area, w^* flexural displacement, x abscissa, t time. Boundary conditions are :

$$x = 0 \text{ (clamping end)} \quad \frac{\partial w(0,t)}{\partial x} = w(0,t) = 0$$

At the free end $x = L$, additional mass m is not reduced to ideal punctual mass. It is distributed along a distance l . Shear force and flexural moment are I being rotational inertia moment.

$$EI \frac{\partial^3 w^*}{\partial x^3} = m \frac{\partial^2 w^*}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\partial^3 w^*}{\partial t^2 \partial x} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$EI \frac{\partial^2 w^*}{\partial t^2} = -J \frac{\partial^3 w^*}{\partial t^2 \partial x} - \frac{1}{2} m \left[\frac{\partial^2 w^*}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\partial^3 w^*}{\partial t^2 \partial x} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

At resonance frequency f_r , (1) gives Young modulus

$$|E^*| = \frac{\rho S \omega^2 L^4}{I \beta^4}, \quad \omega = 2\pi f_r \quad (4)$$

β is a coefficient depending on boundary conditions (2) and (3). Damping is evaluated by bandwidth method (3dB attenuation), figure (2)

$$\operatorname{tg} \delta_E = \frac{\operatorname{Im} E^*}{\operatorname{Re} E^*} = \frac{\Delta f}{f_r} \quad (5)$$

(4) and (5) constitute two damage indicators during fatigue test. Sample is excited at the clamped end by electrodynamic shaker which is controlled by power amplifier and signal generator whose frequency is adjusted and measured accurately by digital frequency meter. Displacement amplitude at clamped end $w(0,t)$ is measured by means of a contactless displacement transducers. Displacement at the free end $w(L,t)$ is measured also by a pair of contactless transducers. Sample and shaker are inside a box whose walls are covered with polystyrene layers. Acoustical isolation is then ensured. To prevent heating, forced cooling of shaker is necessary. The maximum normal stress is produced at clamping end $\sigma_{11} = \frac{Mz}{I}$, $z = \frac{h}{2}$

M flexural moment

$$\sigma_{11 \max} = \frac{24 \pi^2 f_r^2 m W_{\max} (L) \cdot L}{bh^2} \quad (6)$$

(6) is evaluated from displacement $W(L)$ at the free end, additional mass and resonance frequency f_r .

In the flexural test described, the mean stress is zero.

III LOCAL EVALUATION OF DAMAGE

Complex Young modulus $|E^*|$ and $\operatorname{tg} \delta_E$ are global dynamic damage indicators concerning the whole sample. We suggest local damage indicators based on ultrasonic wave propagation methods. Using transmitted progressive waves (longitudinal or transverse) through the thickness of the sample, we can evaluate, figure (3), the corresponding velocity $v_{i/j}^*$ h thickness, t propagation time, subscript i indicates wave polarisation and j propagation direction

$$|v_{i/j}^*| = \frac{h}{t}, \quad C_{ijij}^* = \rho (v_{i/j}^*)^2 \quad (7)$$

With two pairs of transducers, one for longitudinal wave, the other for transverse wave, we can evaluate three velocities (one longitudinal and two transverse) and consequently we can obtain three complex rigidity moduli $C_{ijkl}^* = \rho (v_{i/j}^*)^2$. If (3) is thickness direction, (2) is

width direction and (1) is along sample axis, we can obtain C^*_{3333} , C^*_{3131} , C^*_{3232} .

Damping related to the modulus is evaluated via wave attenuation.

IV MATHEMATICAL MODELS FOR ACCELERATED TESTING

With viscoelastic constituents of composite material, it is necessary to use appropriate mathematical models incorporating combined influence of temperature T , frequency f , thermal stress level σ_T and athermal stress σ_i , number of cycles N etc. Generalized Eyring model, [1]

Akay-Saibel model, or equivalence temperature-frequency, Rotem, [2] are some of the possible theoretical frameworks. For refractory advanced composites (such as carbon-carbon or carbon-SiC), matrix is nearly elastic even for local heating which produces temperature increase not exceeding 100°C . We suggest the following empirical expression to correlate maximum stress S and the fatigue life N

$$e^{mS} N = D \quad (8)$$

D and m being constants to be evaluated from fatigue curve.

V SOME EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Two sets of samples are tested. The first set corresponds to virgin samples of Carbon-SiC composite. The sample is divided into three zones 1, 2, 3. Ultrasonic measurements are effected. During fatigue test, Young modulus $|E^*|$ and damping capacity $\text{tg } \delta_E$ are evaluated periodically. Beyond 10^7 cycles, fatigue test is stopped and ultrasonic measurements are effected locally.

Figure (4) represents variation of E^* and $\text{tg } \delta_E$ vs N number of cycles. Damage is followed by decrease of E^* and increase of $\text{tg } \delta_E$.

Figure (5) represents variation of rigidity modulus C^*_{3333} before and after fatigue test. Regular decrease of modulus is noticed.

In some samples, decrease of dynamic moduli (E^* or C^*_{3333}) is not observed at the beginning of the test as shown in the figures (6). Damping decreases with N in the first stage. Ultrasonic measurements indicated strengthening effect; figure (7). This behaviour can be explained by reducing of void percentage during flexural vibration test. The second set of samples concerns post proof fatigue tests. Samples were first submitted to extensional fatigue tests. Samples in the next stage were submitted to accelerated fatigue test using flexural vibrations.

Figures (8) shows a regular decrease of Young modulus $|E^*|$ vs. number of cycles N . Damping capacity $\text{tg } \delta_E$ shows variations with maxima and minima. It could be interpreted as a possible "adaptation" of the material with eventual reducing of void percentage (minima) and damping by solid friction caused by delamination (maxima). Such fluctuations were perceived when measuring attenuation around resonance. A non-linear behaviour consecutive to softening of rigidity combined with solid friction is perceived as shown in figure (9). Figure (9) shows that damage is noticed only in the zone (2) meanwhile zones 1 and 3 present a strengthening behaviour.

VI CONCLUDING REMARKS

. Accelerated fatigue testing using flexural vibrations of clamped-free

rod at resonance frequency is an experimental set-up easy to carry out.
 . Dynamic damage indicators based on Young modulus and related damping permit global evolution of damage of the whole sample.

. Ultrasonic measurements of rigidity complex moduli C^*_{ijij} furnish quantitative indicators which characterize local damages.

. Fatigue behaviour of advanced composites with refractory matrix can be different from that of classical composites, in the sense that the first stage of fatigue life may correspond to a strengthening period.

[1] Eyring - Encyclopedia of Science and tech. Vol.7 p 357

[2] Rotem A (1981) Fatigue behaviour of graphite-epoxy - ASTMST723 p 152-173

Figure 1) (a) Clamped-free flexural rod with additional mass is used for fatigue testing.
 (b) Schematic diagram of experimental set-up. Sample is excited at frequency resonance and flexural displacement $w(L)$ is maintained constant during fatigue test by electronic circuit.

Figure (2) : Damping capacity is evaluated by bandwidth evaluation of resonance curve.

Figure (3) : (a) Ultrasonic methods use transmitted progressive waves through the sample thickness. (b) Ultrasonic measurements are used as local damage indicators in the three zones of each sample.

Figure (4) : Dynamic flexural Young modulus E^*_1 (absolute value) and damping capacity $\text{tg } \delta_E$ vs number of cycles. Maximum principal stress $\sigma_{11 \text{ max}} = S = 260 \text{ MPa}$.

Figure (5) : Rigidity complex modulus C_{3333}^* in the three zones of the sample. Maximum principal stress $S = 450 \text{ MPa}$.

Figure (6) : Fatigue test on sample of (C | SiC) composite. The first stage corresponds to the strengthening. Beyond 10^7 cycles, damage occurs. Maximum stress $S = 260$ MPa.

Figure (7) : Rigidity complex modulus C_{3333}^* in the three zones. Local strengthening is noticed on the damping curve.

Figure (8) : Post proof fatigue test -(C - SiC) composite sample. Flexural fatigue test - Curve of Young modulus shows regular decrease of E^* meanwhile damping oscillates; Maximum stress $S = 250$ MPa.

Figure (9) : Ultrasonic measurements on the sample in figure (8). Local damage varies from one zone to the other.